

GENDER IN EDUCATION

GENDER SEGREGATION IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION AND SCIENCE IN BULGARIA IN COMPARISON WITH THE EU TENDENCIES

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ABSTRACT: The establishment of fair European research area with a view to gender equality is one of the main requirements of Europe 2020 Strategy. In that context the paper presents selected results of a study of the gender balance in the higher education and science in Bulgaria. Problems concerning the position of the country in the European map of gender equality in the two academic sectors and especially the level of gender segregation are treated. Three intrinsic problems are identified - horizontal segregation by fields of science, tendency towards men leaving the public research sector, and substantial vertical segregation by academic and leading positions.

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Introduction

Gender equality in the higher education and science and achievement of gender balance within academia is one of the main problems with a view to the establishment of fair European research area as a requirement of Europe 2020 Strategy. In that context the evaluation of the position of Bulgaria in Europe by gender equality in the academic community and especially of the level of gender segregation was done as a part of a study within the framework of the scientific and research program of the Economic Research Institute at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.

The analysis proves that Bulgaria has a decent place on the European map for Gender Equality in academic sphere, with obviously achieved progress reflecting the refocused priorities from achievement of gender equality to balanced participation of men and women. Many of the existing problems in this field, average in Europe and in different countries, have been practically overcome in Bulgaria. However, the most visible problem area was identified - gender segregation in both academic sectors. In spite of its different level, this phenomenon is common for whole Europe.

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The analyses and evaluations in the paper are based on the statistical information published in the four (since 2003) three-year reports of European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation at the European Commission - "She figures" ("She figures", 2009, 2012; EC, 2003, 2006). The last available data, published in "She figures" - 2012, are for 2009-2010. Calculations for 2011-2012 are from NSI data (www.nci.bg).

Horizontal gender segregation

Unlike the relatively equal average distribution of male and female researchers in higher education and science in Bulgaria (participation of women was 47.7% in 2009 and 49% in 2011 versus 33% average for EU-27 in 2009), there are significant disproportions in their participation by scientific fields and disciplines. There is a substantial imbalance in the gender participation or the so-called horizontal gender segregation.

Concerning PhD graduates, according to latest data for EU-27 in 2010, clearly feminized are the science fields traditional for women - they were 64% of the PhD graduates in education, 56% in medicine and 54% in the humanities and arts. There was a relatively balanced gender composition only in the social sciences (including business and law), where 49% of PhD graduates were women, as well as in agriculture and veterinary, where women were 52%. Significant masculinization exists mainly in the life and physical sciences, mathematics and computing, where female PhD graduates were less than 26%, as well as in engineering, including manufacturing and construction (40% are women). The information on Bulgaria is substantially different than the European.

TABLE 1. PROPORTION OF FEMALE PHD GRADUATES IN BULGARIA IN ALL PHD GRADUATES BY BROAD FIELD OF STUDY (%)

Field of science	2003	2006	2010
Education	52.2	52.0	47.0
Humanities and arts	68.4	68.0	57.0
Social sciences, business and law	50.0	58.0	51.0
Life and physical sciences, mathematics and computing	52.8	56.0	58.0
Engineering	31.4	33.0	32.0
Agriculture and veterinary	46.4	54.0	80.0
Medicine	56.4	56.0	43.0

Source: "She figures" - 2006, p.39; 2009, p.51; 2012, p.54.

Data in Table 1 show that in the beginning of the analyzed period Bulgaria was in a different situation than Europe, mainly concerning female PhD graduates in the field of natural sciences, where the feminization continues to increase in the next years as well. In 2006 there was a deeper lack of desire in men to advance in the academic field. Engineering remained the only field of science where they dominate.

At the end of the period the situation concerning the movement towards balanced gender distribution of PhD graduates by fields of science improved, except in agriculture and natural sciences, where female domination reached "unhealthy" values.

More detailed information on different scientific fields shows that in 2010 women were 66% of the PhD graduates in life sciences, 51% in physics, 56% in mathematics and statistics, and reached 50% in architecture and construction. In this context, the leadership of Bulgaria regarding the European desires and tendencies towards

achieving gender equality in traditionally “male” scientific fields goes to another extreme - weakening desire in young men to pursue academic career. This requires undertaking relevant encouraging measures in regards to the interests of the science itself, as well as its gender composition.

This tendency exists also in the analysis of the *shares of female researchers in the total number, disaggregated by fields of science and sectors*, mainly in the government sector for science.

TABLE 2. PROPORTION OF FEMALE RESEARCHERS IN BULGARIA IN THE NUMBER OF RESEARCHERS BY SECTOR (IN HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR - HES; GOVERNMENT SECTOR FOR SCIENCE - GS) BY FIELD OF SCIENCE (%)

Scientific directions	2003		2006		2009	
	HES	GS	HES	GS	HES	GS
Natural sciences	55.0	51.6	55.0	54.0	42.0	52.0
Engineering and technologies	24.4	34.3	22.0	33.0	31.0	38.0
Medical sciences	55.6	51.2	53.0	53.0	45.0	70.0
Agricultural sciences	35.9	52.7	41.0	53.0	39.0	60.0
Social sciences	40.1	59.3	43.0	58.0	51.0	57.0
Humanities	52.4	66.2	58.0	63.0	54.0	66.0

Source: “She figures” - 2006, p.42, 44; 2009, pp.57, 60; 2012, pp.66, 71.

Analysis of the presented in Table 2 data denies the settled in the society fallacy concerning the strong feminization of the *higher education sector*: in 2003-2009 there was a clear tendency towards more balanced gender composition of such scientific fields in the higher schools like natural sciences, engineering, agricultural, medical and social sciences, with relevant decrease of the feminization or increase in the share of women in fields where they have been significantly behind the male lecturers. This means that the higher education sector remains attractive to both genders, either due to the satisfactory payment, or to the prestige of the profession and/or acceptable work conditions and working time.

At the same time men show more and more neglected participation in the government sector for science, i.e. in *budget research institutions*. Except the engineering and technologies, all scientific fields are obviously feminized. In medical, agricultural, social sciences and humanities the shares of female researchers varies between 60-70%. Obviously, the low prestige of the profession “researcher” first of all because of the unsatisfactory payment in the public research sector in Bulgaria provoke men to leave and look for work in the private research sector or in other employment areas.

We have to mention that bending the gender balance in any direction harms the economy of the country, which should fully use the professional research potential of both men and women for achieving progress in meeting the targets of Europe 2020 Strategy and establishing knowledge economy.

In a concentrated form the horizontal gender segregation by science fields in higher education and science is presented through the values of the calculated since 2003 *dissimilarity index* (Table 3).

“She figures” - 2003 Report measured for a first time dissimilarity index for the whole academic sphere (p.58). Its value for Bulgaria in 2000 placed the country on 1st place (in a negative sense) in Europe with its highest level of 0.31. Deciphering the index means that 1/3 of the lecturers and researchers should change their scientific field, so that there will be a progress in the gender equality in the academic institutions in

Bulgaria through practical realization of the EU criterion for that period - achieving 35% female participation in every scientific field.

TABLE 3. DISSIMILARITY INDEX - DI

	2003	2006	2009
<i>EU MEMBER COUNTRIES</i>	DI - EC-25	DI - EC-27	DI - EC-27
Higher education sector	0.14	0.14	-
Government sector for science	0.21	0.18	-
<i>BULGARIA</i>			
Higher education sector	0.23	0.27	0.16
Government sector for science	0.12	0.14	0.15

Source: "She figures" - 2006, p.48; 2009, p.64; 2012, p.77.

The further detailing of the dissimilarity index and its measuring in higher education and public research sectors shows significant improvement of their gender composition, especially in higher education. The 2009 results mean that respectively only 16 and 15% of lecturers and researchers in both sectors in Bulgaria should change the science field of their position for achieving balanced gender distribution. Determining the gender of people hypothetically "leaving", as well of segregated in these fields, is in accordance with the data on their participation in the respective sectors. In this sense, based on the results in Table 2, we may conclude, that in higher education average for all scientific fields 16% of men should "move", while in the government sector for science - 15% of women.

Vertical gender segregation

The existence of strong vertical gender segregation is one of the most substantial problems in the higher education and science both in Europe and in Bulgaria.

TABLE 4. PROPORTIONS OF WOMEN AND MEN IN A TYPICAL ACADEMIC CAREER*, EU-27 (%)

Gender	PhD graduates	Grade D	Grade B	Grade A
2002				
Women	41	40	33	16
Men	59	60	64	84
2006				
Women	45	44	36	18
Men	55	56	67	82
2010				
Women	46	44	37	20
Men	54	56	63	80

Source: "She figures" - 2009, p.73; 2012, p.88.

Note: * The European statistics presents data for four types of academic positions - grade A, B, C, D. As mentioned in "She figures" - 2009 Report, in Bulgaria valid are three of them: A - full professor; B - associated professor and D - assistant.

The vertical segregation by academic staff positions/scientific ranks is shown most clearly in the analysis of the trajectories of professional career of men and women in academia. Data in Table 4 (average for EU-27) show increasing difference in the proportions of women and men in moving to higher academic positions. With relative gender balance at the start of academic career, achieving grade B and mostly grade A becomes "a stumbling block" in the career development of women in the academic fields. Despite the slight closing of the scissors in the analyzed period, the difference, particularly for grade A, remains more than significant.

Slowing the academic career of women can be traced also by *scientific degrees*. According to NSI data for 2011, the share of women with PhD and DrSc degrees was 41.7% of female research personnel with higher education and of men - 48% of male research personnel with higher education in Bulgaria. In spite of the slightly lower participation of men in all research personnel with higher education (49.3%), the share of men with scientific degrees of the respective personnel is higher than the one for women by 6 points - 52.8%.

The stated differences in favor of men are confirmed also by the quite slowly changing values of the *glass ceiling index*. By this index Bulgaria is substantially above (in a positive sense) the EU average level (Table 5). This does not deny the existence of vertical segregation by academic positions in Bulgaria - the glass ceiling continues to weigh on the heads of the female researchers, but it is considerably "thinner" than in most European countries.

TABLE 5. GLASS CEILING INDEX IN THE ACADEMIC FIELD

Countries	2004	2007	2010
EU-27	1.90	1.80	1.80
Bulgaria	1.73	1.50	1.40

Source: "She figures" - 2006, p.59; 2009, p.78; 2012, p.96.

This index was presented to the science community in 2006, while the first "She figures" Report in 2003 measured the so-called *feminization ratio* among senior (grade A) academic staff - number of female grade A per 100 male grade A staff. According to 2001 data, Bulgaria was on the 2nd place among the EU member candidates (behind Latvia) with value of this indicator of 21.7. The country was close to the "leaders" in the then EU-15 like Portugal (23.9) and Finland (23.4), which means that little more than 20 women per 100 men were in the "top positions" of the academic hierarchy. Obviously the women are strongly segregated, but the data for other European countries report substantially worse results - about 10 women per 100 male full professors.

TABLE 6. PERCENTAGE OF GRADE A STAFF (FULL PROFESSORS)
 OF ACADEMIC STAFF IN BULGARIA BY GENDER (%)

Years	Women	Men
2001	3.7	13.1
2004	4.0	13.0
2007	5.0	14.0
2010	6.0	15.0

Source: "She figures" - 2003, p.64; 2006, p.58; 2009, p.77; 2012, p.92.

The values of the lately calculated glass ceiling index, particularly for 2010, place Bulgaria on the 5th place (in a positive sense) among the European countries. However, the considerably good state of the country does not deny the existence and maintaining in time of the problem of vertical segregation, which is shown in the analysis of the participation of women on higher academic position in the typical career of the researchers.

Data in Table 6 on the *share of grade A staff (full professors) of academic staff* in Bulgaria show significant, though decreasing, majority of men: in the four studied years their number exceeds the number of female full professors respectively 3.5, 3.25, 2.8 and 2.5 times.

The information on the *proportion of female grade A academics among all grade A academics* is even more indicative in this aspect: 18% in 2001 and 2004, 24% in 2007, and 25.9% in 2010. Despite the obvious progress in the number of career “advancing” women, they are little over 1/4 of all grade A academics. Significantly better, though not entirely equal, is the situation with the grade B academics: the proportion of women there was 40% in 2010, which was 5.1% higher than in 2004. The more difficult and slow process of professional advancing of women in higher education and science is seen also by their “leading” positions at grade D staff level. Their share in all grade D staff shows surprising persistency - in the four years from 2004 to 2007 it increased only by 1.6%, and since then it has maintained the “leading” place of 54% till 2010. These tendencies are even more negative regarding the female segregation, when we have in mind their increasing share in all researchers from 43.4% in 2001 to 46% in 2010 and 48% in 2012.

Despite the long awaited Law on Academic Staff in Bulgaria, in force since May 2010, the analysis of the proportion of men and women by academic staff position in the following period shows the indestructible stable character of the outlined above tendencies, which can be traced regarding the higher education sector (Table 7).

TABLE 7. PROPORTION OF WOMEN IN ALL RESEARCHERS IN STATE AND PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN BULGARIA BY ACADEMIC POSITIONS (%)

Academic Positions	2010/2011	2011/2012	2012/2013
Grade A academics	25.9	26.6	29.4
Grade B academics	39.7	40.8	41.7
Grade D academics	51.1	52.4	53.0
Teachers and research fellows	61.7	63.2	61.0

Source: calculated by NSI data, www.nsi.bg.

The share of female grade A academics increased only by 3.5% and due to the low “start” level remained under 1/3 of all academics on this position, despite the fact that the absolute number of female grade A academics in the three academic years showed high increase of 39% compared with the one of men (17%). Whether it is a beginning of positive changes towards overcoming the vertical segregation of women by academic positions or it is a temporary phenomenon as a reaction of the delayed simplification of procedures for academic career, only time will tell.

Practically the influence of the mentioned new Law on gender distribution of grade B academics is unseen - the share of women on this position increased only by 2%. The same was the increase in the share of the “working bees” in the higher education - women grade D academics, still dominating at the lowest level of the academic hierarchy. Even more “representative” is the participation of women in category “teachers and research fellows” - people without scientific degree and probably without obvious academic perspective. Their share exceeded 60%, and there are no any signs in the years of dropping under this “threshold” (63.8% in 2000, 68.4% in 2006, 63.2% in 2011 and 61% in 2012).

Data of the number of *men and women grade A academics in the European countries by age groups* are indicative (in 2010 the available information is only for 12 countries, including Bulgaria). As in most of them, in Bulgaria as well the biggest number of grade A academics is in age group above 55. Only in Germany the number of men and women grade A academics is bigger in age group 45-54. It is interesting that in Austria, Romania and Belgium the number of female grade A academics is bigger than the male in the age group 45-54. We have to underline that in Germany, Austria, Italy and Romania there is a registered significant number of men and women

grade A academics aged 35-44, while in Bulgaria there are lower opportunities for professional career for the younger generations. Among the researchers aged 35-44 in Bulgaria the number of men and women grade A academics is equal - 5 persons. In comparison, in Romania their number is 1165 for women and 1294 for men, in Germany - 560 for women and 2293 for men, in Italy - 108 for women and 460 for men, in Austria - 93 for women and 281 for men. In accordance, we can draw the conclusion that in Bulgaria the academic career has slow rates for both genders, but women are in more unfavorable situation than men also in temporal sense, since their number is only 1/4 of the one of men grade A academics even in age group over 55.

Besides by academic positions, there is a *vertical segregation by highest hierarchical levels* (top-positions) of the academic career. A landmark for evaluation of the male and female participation in the management is the determined by the EU Strategy for Equality between Women and Men (2010-2015) (EC, 2010) target of achieving 25% participation of women in top hierarchy positions in the higher education and research sectors, as well as target of at least 40% participation of one gender in the scientific boards in academic structures and commissions and expert groups at European Commission in this field.

The disproportionate *participation of women and men in the scientific boards*, as seen from the data in Table 8, shows not only insufficient representativeness of women and lack of a fair competition between the genders for these positions, but also their weak desire to “overcome” the still insurmountable glass ceiling effect. Paradox is that the latter is specific not only of men but also of women who consciously or not do not understand their “defrauded” situation. Having in mind the elective character of the respective positions and already mentioned balanced participation of female researchers in the higher education and science in Bulgaria, the following conclusion can be drawn: the insufficient participation of women in the management of the research activities to some extent is a result of the fact that women, on one hand, do not apply enough for certain positions, and on the other hand, they nominate and tend to elect male candidates. However, such behavior is rather a reaction to the settled social-cultural gender stereotypes than to professional-organizational or institutional barriers before science career of women.

TABLE 8. PROPORTION OF WOMEN ON SCIENTIFIC BOARDS
 IN RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS AND UNIVERSITIES (%)

Countries	2001	2004	2007	2010
EU-27	27.3*	-	22.0	36.0**
Bulgaria	14.7	32.8	37.0	29.0

Source: “She figures” - 2003, p.76; 2006, p.71; 2009, p.99; 2012, p.117.

Note: * Data for EU-15; average for 11 EU candidates is 19.1. ** As mentioned in the “She figures” - 2012 Report, this result is slightly increased due to some methodological changes in measuring the average indexes for EU-27 compared with the “She figures” - 2009.

Presented in Table 8 data for Bulgaria show a serious increase of female participation in the analyzed period from one of the lowest levels average in EU-15 and the 11 candidates in 2001 to the highest level (33%) among EU-27 in 2004 after Norway (48%) and Denmark (35%) and even to 37% in 2007. However, it remains under the defined target of 40% participation. In 2010 there was a substantial drop by 8 points in Bulgaria. It positions the country far from the average level in Europe, which is closer and closer to reaching the envisioned target. Nevertheless only in four European countries it has already been reached - Iceland (40%), Finland (45%), Norway (46%) and Sweden (49%). For information, Poland and Cyprus are at the

bottom of the ranking by this indicator - only 7% of women there participate in scientific boards in the relevant institutions.

Much more visible are the *gender differences in participation in management boards of academic institutions*. The proportion of female heads of institutions in the higher education sector increased from 8% in 2007 to 14.4% in 2010. However, with another 15 countries it remained under the EU-27 average level (15.5% in 2010). It is absolutely insufficient both for Europe and Bulgaria in regard to the mentioned target of achieving 25% participation of female heads of institutions in academic sphere. We have to note that in such a scale the female participation is reached only in three European countries - Finland (25%), Sweden (26.9%) and Norway (31.8%), while in Latvia it is 0, despite the fact that this country is among the few with highest female academic employment (over 50%). This raises again the question about the relation between the gender stereotypes settled in the society and the low self-esteem of women, specific as well of the countries with not so striking but still exceptionally low results by this indicator.

Even more indicative is the information about the *proportion of female heads of universities or assimilated institutions based on capacity to deliver PhD*. In 2007 it was 9% both in EU-27 and Bulgaria, with quite insignificant increase to respectively 10 and 12% in 2010. Leaders are again the Scandinavian countries, where unlike the rest of Europe female heads of universities are not an exception: Sweden - 43%, Iceland - 33%, Norway - 29% and Finland - 25%. There are also countries where the term "female head of university" is totally unknown phenomenon - Cyprus, Lithuania and Hungary with 0% of women on this position.

The newer data for Bulgaria support the outlined tendencies. The proportion of female directors of institutes at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS) as a main representative of the *government sector for science* is 21.7%. They are 10 women among totally 46 directors - 6 of them are in the traditionally feminized scientific fields as social sciences and humanities and arts, and only 4 are female directors in the life and physical sciences and engineering (BAS, 2011).

The "progress" of women can be observed with the decrease of the level of top positions in BAS - the lower is the level of the position, the higher is the share of women: 40.9% are female deputy directors and 70% are scientific secretaries. Composing scientific boards remains under the criterion determined by EU - women are 36.6% of all chairpersons of scientific councils in the BAS institutes. Despite the fact that since 1869 there has not been any woman - president of BAS, the central management bodies of the academy in 2011-2012 register certain progress in achieving balanced gender representativeness. Ratio of number of BAS deputy president men and women changed from 3:0 to 1:2; of number of scientific secretaries by scientific fields - from 5:2 to 4:3; of shares of members of the Management Board - from 40:60% to 50:50%, i.e. a full parity between women and men is achieved only at this position. The positions President of BAS and Chairperson of the General Assembly of BAS are still a "trade mark" for male scientists. The female participation among the academicians and corresponding members of BAS remains quite low: having in mind the newly elected BAS members in 2012, the share of women is only 3% of the academicians (2 women among all 68 academicians) and 14% of corresponding members (13 women of all 93, and 7 of them are again in the social sciences and humanities and arts).

The situation in the management boards in the *higher education* is quite the same. The elected in 2012 new Council of Heads of the higher schools in Bulgaria has a Chairman (in the literal sense of the word) and 6 members of the Management Board (also men). In accordance with the data from the Register of accredited higher schools at the Ministry of Education, Youth and Science, as at 1st May 2013, in 51 state and private universities and higher schools female heads are only 2, i.e. 3.9% of all heads

(the heads are also chairpersons of the Academic Councils). Women deputy heads are 32. It is not enough regarding the fact that the average number of deputy heads in a higher school varies between 2 and 4. Except this, women are deputy heads mainly on international cooperation, public relations and education activity, but no one on scientific policy of the institution. Among the chairpersons of General Assembly (highest management body in the higher schools) women again are only 2, but the number of women deputy chairpersons of General Assembly is significant. It means that the mentioned "inverse progress" of women is specific of the whole academic sphere in Bulgaria.

Conclusion

As a result of the study of gender aspects of the higher education and science in Bulgaria, three intrinsic problem areas were identified:

- horizontal segregation by fields of science and disciplines especially in the research sector;
- tendency towards men leaving the government sector for science, which leads to the strengthening feminization of science;
- substantial vertical segregation by academic and leading positions in both academic sectors.

It has to be underlined that unlike gender segregation either horizontal or vertical existing in all European countries the second indicated problem area is peculiar for Bulgarian academic reality. It requires the future development and applying of further ways and mechanisms for their overcoming. The creation of a suitable fair gender climate in academia is of great importance for the building of a knowledge economy as well as for the successful integration of the country into the European educational and research areas.

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